

Understanding the experiences of parents in developing interest and talent of children

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ABSTRACT

Every child has a talent that is ready to be developed. However, not all parents know how to identify and develop it. Purpose of the study is to explore and analyze the experiences of parents in developing interest and talent of children. In order to obtain factual data on parenting, a qualitative method was used. Data collection was carried out by in-depth interviews and open to seven parents of talented children. The data obtained were analyzed in five stages, namely transcribing the results of interviews, taking inventory of important statements, classifying meanings, describing and constructing the essence of the subject's experience, and making research reports. There were three main findings of this research, namely: i) parents in nurturing for talented children have the characteristics of an authoritative style, where demands and responses were carried out in a balanced manner, ii) the development of children's interest and talent was carried out by parents by guiding and training independently, taking lessons, and various competitions, and iii) limited time and energy were the main obstacles for parents in nurturing and developing children's interest and talent.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The position of children in the family is very important. Apart from being a perfect marriage, children are the next generation of their parents in the future. The presence of a child is expected by every parent because it is a sign of the perfection of a marriage [1]. On the other hand, a child is a mandate from God that must be guarded and nurtured as well as possible in order to grow and develop properly.

Parents as the children's closest environment have the obligation to nurture and develop their potential, interests and talents. It is believed that every child is a genius [2]. This paradigm arises due to a view that children born into the world have certain talents and intelligence, although only one or two are the most dominant [3]. Various studies on the brain show that children from birth to eight years are a period of very rapid brain growth and development [4]. The period of rapid brain development occurs in the first few years of life [5], [6]. By the time a child reaches age 5, more than 100 billion neurons have made connections in the cerebral cortex [7]. In the early stages of life, a child's brain creates amazing new neural connections every second [8]. When a child enters kindergarten age, his brain weighs almost 90% of that of an adult [9]. This extraordinary brain development is highly dependent on the environment. If the environment provides positive stimulation, the brain will develop properly and can affect children's talents and intelligence.

The first and foremost task in developing children's interests and talents is the parents. The form of parental treatment and stimulation can affect children's intelligence. Parental involvement in early childhood care and education and early intervention services has a positive effect on their children's achievement [10]. Parents have a vital role in providing the early stimulation the brain needs for proper development [11]. In addition, parents have various opportunities to identify their children's interests in various objects and activities in the early life of children [12]. Every child has a treasure inside, like the message that Allah gave him. The task of parents is only to help find it, and then develop it so that the child reaches the best condition. Parents must be able to develop various intelligence of children as a whole, and pay attention to children's interest and talent so that they can get achievements they are proud of.

Parents who are sensitive and care about the various needs of early childhood can help their children's confidence and achievement. Frobel likens parents and educators to gardeners [13], where the role of a gardener is to care for, and fertilize his plants so that they can grow and produce fruit or seeds that are ready to be harvested. For this reason, parents must be good caretakers for the growth and development of their children.

Parent is an important external factor in children's cognitive development [14]. Parenting patterns can affect various kinds of children's intelligence [12]. Skilled parenting can stimulate children's intellectual development [5], [6]. Parenting is also able to optimize the potential of the child, direct the child to the achievement of welfare, and assist the child in completing developmental tasks properly [11]. There are four influences of parents after the child is born, namely: i) providing a protective environment to reduce risks; ii) providing experiences that lead to the development of maximum potential; iii) becoming an advisor in the larger community; and iv) becoming an irreplaceable force in children's lives [12]. John Locke revealed that development comes from stimuli that children receive from parents and caregivers, as well as through the experiences they get from the environment [15], [16]. If the child's environment is positive, it will indirectly have a positive impact on their development and vice versa. Based on this explanation, it can be understood that parenting styles have an important role in developing various potentials, interests, and talents of children.

This research aimed to dig up actual information on parents in nurturing and developing children's interest and talent. The various experiences of these parents can be a reference in parenting. Unfortunately, this research is still limited in number. Through phenomenological research, it is hoped that it can provide insight and scientific contributions in nurturing and developing interest and talent of children.

2. METHOD

To reveal various phenomena and obtain factual data about the styles of parents in caring for and developing children's interests and talents, this research used a qualitative method with a phenomenological approach. Various parental experiences can be revealed and obtain a meaningful description according to the views of the informants when carried out using a phenomenological approach [17]. The researchers in this phenomenological approach attempted to understand the meaning of events and interactions with someone in certain situations. With this approach, it is hoped that parenting patterns that can be adopted by parents to develop interest and talent of early childhood can be found.

2.1. Participants

Participants in this research involved four families selected by purposive sampling. The selection criteria are family or parents who have early childhood with special gifts and talents. This refers to the gifted criteria of children which include above average abilities, high creativity and commitment to tasks [18], [19]. Each participant is represented by a biological mother. The choice of biological mothers is because they are more dominant and have a very important role in parenting than fathers. Mothers are considered to play an important role that greatly influences a child's social, emotional and cognitive growth and development [20], [21]. The three biological mothers who became participants were the biological mother of child A (P1), the biological mother of child B (P2), and the biological mother of child C (P3).

Participant P1 was chosen because she has a gifted child who excels in fashion and singing. Participant P2 was chosen because she has a gifted child who excels in coloring and mathematics. Participant P3 was chosen because she has a gifted child who excels in coloring. The description of each participant can be seen in Table 1.

2.2. Data collection technique

Data collection in this research was carried out by means of open and in-depth interviews with all participants. This technique was chosen because the researchers wanted to get as much complete information as possible from the participants so that their experiences in caring for and developing children's interest and talent could be revealed. Interviews were conducted at each participant's house for three to five days according to the completeness of the information obtained.

Tabel 1. Description of research participants

No	Participants	Age	Interest and talent of children	Children achievement
1.	P1	44 years old	Fashion and singing	Achieving 69 awards in fashion shows and 36 awards in singing
2.	P2	31 years old	Coloring and mathematics	Achieving 72 awards in coloring and 10 awards in mathematics
3.	P3	35 years old	Coloring	Achieving 63 awards in coloring

2.3. Procedure

The first step in conducting this research was determining the participants. Information about participants was obtained by visiting schools and asking teachers about students who have certain gifts and talents. Then, the teacher introduced the parents of each child and provided a contact number for further communication. Before being determined to be a participant, each parent was asked whether she was willing to be a research subject by filling out a statement letter. After the participants agreed, and then it was determined about the interview time at any time of their convenience. In this interview process, a recording device and notes were used to document every conversation and information provided by the participants. Each interview was conducted for two to three hours and was conducted for three to five days.

The interview data that have been obtained were then analyzed by transcribing in written form, taking inventory of the participants' important statements, classifying them according to the existing themes, and constructing the meaning and essence of each participant's experience. From this series of analysis processes, it took the longest time to transcribe the results of the interview because they had to replay recorded conversations from the participants. This research process ended with a report on the results.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Parents have different experiences in developing their children's interests and talents. Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that there were several ways parents could nurture and develop interest and talent of children. Parenting styles, methods of developing children's talents and obstacles experienced by parents have been revealed in this research.

3.1. Parenting style used by parents

Participants in developing their interests and talents were very evident through their treatment of children in everyday life. Parents really cared and fully supported the development of children's interest and talent. They clearly provided various facilities to support and fulfill children's needs. Participant P1 explained that the facilitation was carried out by taking various lessons according to the children's talents and desire. In addition, they also took time to take and accompany their children in lessons and competitions as the following statement.

"His father always supports him, especially in terms of finance and energy, and gives him enthusiasm in participating in championship competitions. Every time he returns from Surabaya, he takes the time to take the child to join competition. When it comes to determining competitions and child's activities, usually I will do it myself and the father is only informed and asked for consideration" (P1).

The form of financial support is in the form of fees for taking lessons, competition activities and renting clothes for fashion shows. Participant P1 explained that the cost of the tutoring that their child participated in had different costs, likewise with the cost of the competition as he mentioned the following:

"The costs that I spend are very diverse. Some are a bit expensive and some are cheap too. For example, the cost of singing lessons is IDR 50,000 for one hour/meeting. In the fashion show, it is a package of IDR 200,000 for one month/four meetings. For dance lessons, it is also a package of IDR 60,000 every month with two weekly meetings. Not to mention English lessons and jarimatika. Anyway, as long as it is for the development of my child, I will work on it" (P1).

Participants P2 and P3 also demonstrated support for developing children's interest and talent. Like participant P1, P2, and P3 also provided a lot of support both in terms of costs and energy as they gave the following statement:

"For the tuition fees that I spend include: IDR 50,000 with 2 weekly meetings in mathematics lessons, IDR 15,000/meeting in coloring lessons sessions, IDR 150,000/month in reciting Quran lessons, and IDR 200,000/month in English lessons. Besides, I also have to take each child to take lessons" (P3).

“For me, the costs incurred are more to buy coloring supplies and story books, while there is no cost for tutoring, for example, buying crayon Grasp with 48 colors which costs IDR 450,000, faber castell crayons containing 60 costs IDR 130,000, crayons Pascola with 78 colors costs IDR 150,000, Greebel crayons with 48 colors costs IDR 170,000, fluorescent crayons with 12 colors costs IDR 50,000, crayon cutter costs IDR 50,000, crayon crumb cleaner costs IDR 50,000, a white marker costs IDR 15,000, and other equipment, such as tissues, folding tables, pencils, and erasers. In addition, there is also a competition fee which is incurred in the amount of between IDR 10,000 and IDR 50,000 per competition” (P2).

The forms of parental demands include the children’s talents to develop, to be brave children, and to increase children’s insight and gain many achievements. In addition, parents are very disciplined and firm in educating, training, and directing children’s abilities. As for the responses shown by parents in this parenting, parents always enthusiastically take the time to accompany their children in various activities, especially during tutoring and competitions. They give encouragement to their children during competitions, as well as give praise and rewards to their children. In addition, what is no less important is that parents facilitate and fulfill their children’s equipment and needs, both in relation to tutoring and competition needs.

These various statements indicate that each parent has a good response to the development of their children’s interest and talent. They do not only demand children, but also provide the best facilities. Through demands and good responses, children’s interest and talent can develop optimally.

The results showed that if parents’ demands and responses to children’s abilities are balanced, it can affect children’s achievement [22]. Parental support is very important in developing children’s abilities in the field of multiple intelligences. The support provided by parents can foster and build children’s self-confidence. A supportive environment can promote mental health and reinforce child-centered activities. The results of regression analysis reveal that parental support and involvement positively predict children’s academic self-efficacy and self-esteem [23]. By getting support from parents, children feel they get attention, affection, and care. In addition, parental support is seen as a form of approval and appreciation for their abilities.

Parents’ support in developing their children’s abilities can be in the form of moral and material support. Moral support is support related to the mental and feelings of children. For example, this moral support is escorting and accompanying children during lessons or competitions and giving encouragement and praise to children. A supportive environment can be done by parents by spending time with children, interacting pleasantly with children, and supporting and helping children [22]. Parents’ involvement in their child’s learning process provides many opportunities for success, such as increased morale and attitude, academic achievement in all fields, and social behavior and adjustment.

Material support is support related to meeting the physical needs of children, such as costs, facilitating children’s activities, and giving prizes for the children’s achievements [12]. The various material supports are intended to provide stimulus to children, so that they are more enthusiastic and increase their performance. As explained by skinner in his theory of operant conditioning, in this theory, it is emphasized that there is a relationship between stimulus, reinforcement, and response. The response that arises from the stimulus provided can be continuously improved by providing reinforcement. This means that when children are given positive stimulation as well as reinforcement, they can generate positive responses as desired. Watson as a follower of Pavlov explained that individual behavior can be completely shaped according to what the environment wants. Therefore, by providing stimulus and reinforcement in the form of materials and various gifts, it is hoped that children can show their abilities more optimally.

The demands and responses of the parents really determine the parenting style of the parents. Parents who have high demands and responses are more likely to be in an authoritative style [6], [24]. On the other hand, the low demands and responses from the parents are more likely towards uninvolved style. Meanwhile, high demands from parents that are not accompanied by high responses tend to lead to an authoritarian style. Conversely, high responses from parents who are not accompanied by high demands are more likely to lead to permissive styles.

Based on this description, it can be understood that the parenting style of parents in developing children’s interest and talent is authoritative. Apart from having high demands on the development of children’s talents, they also have high responsiveness and concern. Through the demands and a balanced response from the parents, the children’s ability can develop optimally.

3.2. Methods of developing children’s interest and talent

Participants in developing children’s interest and talent have the same characteristics, namely by guiding and participating in competitions. Guiding children was done by participants through exercises that are carried out independently or by involving others in the form of tutoring. Participant P1 explained that in

guiding the interest and talent of their children, it was done by taking lessons. This is so because they did not have the ability so that they were unable to train the children themselves as the following statement:

“My child seems to have talent. If not taking lessons, it is difficult to develop. Therefore, this is the motivation to take lessons so that children’s talents develop. He himself is also happy every time he takes lessons” (P1).

The point is that if the children are not included in tutoring, their talents will be difficult to develop. Even though children already have talents, they must continue to be developed so that they can be optimal. In addition, their children also enjoy taking lessons. By taking lessons, participant P1 hoped that their children’s talents could develop optimally and get many achievements. Participant P1 took various lessons for her children, including singing, dancing, fashion shows, and *jarimatika* as the following statement:

“There are a lot of lessons that my child takes. Starting to sing at Om Franky vocal course, singing at the Purwa Lakshita dance studio, fashion at little star, and jarimatika at Bina Kusuma Semeru Street. In addition, sometimes they also learn to recite Al-Qur’an, especially on Thursday nights” (P1).

These lessons were followed by the child almost every day from Monday to Sunday. Singing lessons were held twice a week. But when approaching the competition, it can be 4 times a week. According to the participant P1 information, this singing lesson has been going on for one year. Fashion show lessons were held once a week, namely every Saturday. But when there will be a competition, it can be 2 times a week. Dance lessons were held twice a week, namely Wednesday and Sunday. But sometimes the day changes according to the agreement. *Jarimatika* lessons were held three times a week, namely Tuesday, Thursday, and Friday. Usually, they were held at 16.00 to 17.00.

In line with that, participant P3 also took her child to lessons so that the child’s interest and talent would develop. It is just that the types of lessons were different, namely coloring, English, and reciting Al-Qur’an as expressed by participant P3. When asked about the lessons her child took, she replied by saying:

“English tutoring, coloring and reciting Al-Qur’an. Two weekly English lessons are held every Wednesday and Thursday. Coloring lessons are held once a week, every Wednesday. Reciting Al-Qur’an lessons are held twice a week, every Thursday and Saturday. Especially for reciting Al-Qur’an lessons, the teacher visits the house” (P3).

The goal of participant P3 took lessons for her child is to develop abilities and mentally train child to be brave as she mentioned the following:

“First, my child takes lessons so that his potential would develop. Then, from a mental perspective, it aims to be brave. He gets more friends there. There are no friends at home. In addition, let there be activities as well” (P3).

These various lessons were followed by the child after school. The implementation time varies from one lesson to another, depending on the agreement between the two parties. By taking her child to the lessons, participant P3 expected that her child’s talents will develop and increase their knowledge and interactions.

Unlike participants P1 and P3, participant P2 did not take lessons for her child. In developing her child’s interest and talent, it is carried out through independent guidance as she said the following.

“I guide and train my child independently and self-taught through YouTube and Google. Usually, I do this in the evening. After maghrib, after reciting Al-Quran and memorizing, my child often watches YouTube, for example about elephants or about rainbows or something to learn. Sometimes my child is also busy learning to color himself” (P2).

There were several reasons for participant P2 not taking her child to lessons, including time constraints, long distances, and having to pay more fees. As she said when asked the reason for not taking lessons for her child, she replied by saying:

“First, I do not take lessons for my child because I cannot find one here. The limitation of going to the city includes time and taking my child to the lessons. I do not have enough time. Second, it aims at getting closer with my child. If my child wants to take lessons, I have to participate so I can teach my own children. Third, there will be more cost for taking lessons” (P2).

From these descriptions, it can be understood that the first method used by the participants in developing children's interest and talent is by taking lessons and mentoring independently. Each participant believes that by guiding and taking lessons children's talent can develop optimally.

The first and foremost method in developing intellectual talent is guiding and training children in learning. In guiding and training, these children can be done by the parents themselves or involve other people or parties. If parents have the ability to guide and train children themselves, and there is more time for children, doing it by themselves is very good for children. However, if parents have limitations, both ability and time, it will be better when involving other parties. The most important thing in this case is that the child's abilities or talents can be well stimulated, so that they can develop optimally. In this method, parents play a role in providing the best service in order to develop children's abilities. Parents fulfill the expected role and socialize children in three ways, namely: i) as interactive partners for children, ii) as direct instructors, and iii) as providers of activities and opportunities that stimulate children's growth [12]. It can be understood that parents in guiding and training their children's abilities can act as partners, teachers or direct trainers or just facilitate and provide activities to develop children's abilities.

As an interactive partner, parents can do it through assistance in learning. Parents can be a place to ask questions and share information about problems faced by children in learning. As instructors, it means that parents can educate and train their own children without involving other people. This may be done when parents have the ability and time to suit the children's needs. As a provider of activities, parents can do it by facilitating children to take part in various course activities or tutoring to support and develop children's abilities.

The various roles performed by these parents are an effort to help children develop their abilities so that they become more optimal. In Vygotsky language, this assistance and intervention is called scaffolding, namely the techniques used to build a bridge between what the children already know and what the children should know [25]. Scaffolding is characterized and consists of activities carried out or provided by parents to support, guide, and stimulate children's interests and talents in order to achieve optimal development. The form of assistance and intervention carried out by parents is to provide guidance and training, as well as facilitate the various needs of the child.

In addition to guiding and taking lessons, the participants also always take children to the competition. The competition aims to measure the ability and train children's courage to perform in front of the crowd. In addition, it is also to increase children's insight and interaction. Participant P1 mentioned that she often took her children to join competitions in singing, fashion, and dancing as she said the following:

“Most often the competitions that my child participates in are singing, fashion, and dancing. My child has participated in other competitions such as mathematics and English but very rarely. Sometimes in one day my child participates in three kinds of competitions at once. For example, in the morning there is a singing competition, in the afternoon it is fashion, and in the evening, it is singing. So, if you have three competitions a day, you often get overwhelmed” (P1).

Participant P1 explained that her child routinely participates in competitions at least twice a month. The competition was held on weekend, on Sundays. Every week his son often wins. The reason for taking the child to competitions is to add experience and relationships. In addition, it also aims to get prizes and award certificates as she said the following:

“My child participates in competitions to have more experience and relationships. Now, sometimes it aims to get money and trophies. But I do not think about it. The most important thing is that their children are happy instead of having no activities at home, mostly just playing” (P1).

Slightly different from participant P1, participant P2 explained that the purpose of taking her child in various competitions is to learn. In addition, it aims to train mental and courage, and develop various abilities of children. By participating in the competition, she hopes to measure her child's ability. As expressed by participant P2 when asked about the purpose of taking her children to join the competition, she replied by saying:

“At first, my child never won the competition, but that's not the main goal. The most important thing is that my child can learn. In addition, it can train children's courage to appear in front of the crowd. Right now, the aim is more to add to the experience. If you can win, thank God. If you cannot, that's okay” (P2).

Meanwhile, participant P3 revealed that the aim of including her child in the competition was to mentally train the child to be brave. This is because in the past her children tended to be quiet as she said the following:

“As with the goal of the lessons, I take my child to join the competition so that the child is brave and mentally strong. My child is very quiet and has a fear of other people. Through these competitions, I

hope that my child will be mentally stronger and have lots of friends so that he will be brave. In addition, it is also to train and develop my child abilities” (P3).

The second method used by parents in developing the abilities of their children is by participating in competitions. This competition is intended to provide opportunities for children to measure children’s abilities with others. Through this competition children can get a lot of experience, motivation, and train their mental or courage to continue to excel. Competition has several advantages. It can help children develop healthy attitudes about winning and losing, can improve, train and improve children’s abilities, and can encourage children to excel [26]. Constructive competition can motivate children to perform better. Competition is a form of motivation that can be a significant driver in learning.

By participating in competitions, children can get many things that cannot be obtained in other activities. By participating in competitions children can get many benefits, including: being able to know their abilities and limitations, being able to set goals, being able to overcome defeats, being able to develop skills, being able to increase popularity, being able to develop competence in a field, being able to practice problem solving, being able to try multiple roles, can learn various rules of the game, and can work with others.

These various explanations provide an understanding that participating in competitions can provide a positive impact on their lives. However, taking children in competitions actually also has a negative impact on children. One of them is that it can cause mental and emotional disturbances to the child, and sometimes children’s competitions are only for the benefit of their parents. Therefore, to reduce the negative impact on children, parents must be wise in including children in various competitions. Parents must accept whatever results the child gets without having to punish and disappoint the child. Make the competition as learning material for children.

3.3. The obstacles experienced by parents

To develop children’s interests and talents, there are always obstacles that parents experience. Based on the results of the interview, it shows that there are three main obstacles experienced by the participants, namely limited energy and time. Participant P1 revealed that the obstacle she complained most about was limited energy. As for time, it is not a problem. As stated by participant P1 when asked about the obstacles in developing her child’s talents, she replied by saying:

“I do not have any problem with time, because I am a house wife. In fact, it is the problem of energy. Sometimes when you are tired, you cannot just sleep and rest” (P1).

This energy barrier is a problem for participant P1 because she has to drive her child alone every day. Starting from going to school, to tutoring, and participating in competition activities. Participant P1’s husband works outside the city so he cannot take and accompany his child in participating in various activities. Participant P1 said that:

“Every day I have to take my children to school at 06.30 and then in the afternoon at 12.00 to 13.30 I have to take singing lessons, and at 16.00 to 17.00 I have to take dance lessons, sometimes jarimatika lessons” (P1).

To overcome the barriers of energy, participant P1 always maintain good body condition. Take time to rest even if it is a little bit. Sometimes she asked for help from her husbands to take their children to lessons or competitions, especially on Saturdays and Sundays. In addition, she always thinks positively that what she does is for the good of the child and always makes the child happy so that he feels a little less tired. Thus, it can be understood that the obstacle experienced by participant P1 was limited energy.

Besides being experienced by participant P1, participant P3 also complained about the lack of energy as she said the following:

“The obstacle is sometimes feeling tired because she has to take the child to school, tutoring, and accompany the child to competitions. But because the child is enthusiastic, I am also excited” (P3).

Participant P3 often experienced fatigue because whenever the child took lessons or took parts in various competitions, she must take the child herself, while the husband has never done it. To overcome this problem, participant P3 asked her husbands to take care of the household, especially when their children took lessons or competitions. In addition, she often shared duties with her husbands in household matters. Thus, it can be understood that the obstacle experienced by participant P3 in developing their children’s interests and talents was limited energy.

The obstacle experienced by participant P2 was limited time. Time constraints were the main obstacle because participant P2 and her husband worked together so they could not have much time to accompany the

child in participating in the competition. Participant P2 explained that the main obstacle she has faced so far is not being able to accompany her child continuously in various activities, especially when the child is participating in competitions as she said:

“The obstacles I experience are usually related to time, because my husband and I have to work from morning to evening. Therefore, sometimes I entrust the child with the teacher in participating in competitions” (P2).

This time barrier was also one of the reasons of participant P2 for not taking her children to tutoring. In addition, the distance is too far from where she lives. Thus, it can be understood that time constraints are a problem in developing interest and talent.

To overcome this time constraint, participant P2 usually asked for help from school teachers to accompany her child in participating in competitions. Because the one available to assist her child was the teacher in school. In addition, some of the competitions her children participated in were on behalf of the school. With the help of participant P2 teacher, it was a little helped and her child’s abilities could also be channeled properly. Thus, it can be understood that the obstacles experienced by participant P1 in developing their children’s interest and talent is limited time.

To overcome these obstacles, parents must be persistent and optimistic, and have high motivation in developing children’s talents. It cannot be denied that in every parenting there will always be obstacles experienced by parents. Persistence can conquer all things [27]. The optimism is the extent to which a person maintains positive expectations for the future. In optimism, there are motivational and emotional components that can influence a person’s actions. Therefore, what parents need to think about when experiencing obstacles is the future and the various abilities that the child has. With any limitations, as long as parents are caring and have strong motivation to develop children’s abilities, they will work hard and try their hardest to overcome these obstacles and limitations. Thus, parents can develop children’s talents optimally.

4. CONCLUSION

To develop the interest and talent of children, it requires appropriate and balanced parenting between demandingness and responsiveness. This parenting style is seen in parents with the authoritative type. Parents must have strong demands on children’s abilities by providing certain targets in each activity. At the same time, parents also provide full support for children’s abilities by guiding and facilitating all their needs to the fullest. Children must be mentored both independently and by taking lessons. In addition, parents should participate in various competitions as a form of training and measure the achievement of children’s interest and talent. Parents must take the time and provide the best service according to the needs and developmental characteristics of the child. Thus, it can be understood that the sensitivity and concern of parents are the top priority so that the interest and talent of children can develop optimally.

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